

Dereddening the Near-Infrared Spectra of L Dwarfs

Vivienne Baldassare, Advisor: Kelle Cruz

Project Dates: September 2010 through May 2011

Introduction

Brown dwarfs are star-like objects that are not hot enough to fuse hydrogen like normal stars. This research focuses on L dwarfs, which are brown dwarfs with effective temperatures between ~ 1300 and 2100 K (Burrows et al. 2001). Brown dwarfs have no relationship between age and mass/temperature, as normal stars do. Because they continuously cool with time, objects of the same age do not necessarily have the same temperature. Thus, we cannot use temperature as a proxy for age for brown dwarfs, and must look to other features to help us assign ages. Low gravity L dwarfs are expected to be young, because they have not finished contracting yet. We can identify these low gravity L dwarfs through certain spectral features. These low gravity objects have redder near-infrared (NIR) spectra than older, normal gravity objects. This is expected to be due to clouds and dust in their atmospheres. We demonstrate that the NIR spectra of young, low gravity L dwarfs look like the spectra of older L dwarfs after the interstellar reddening law has been applied.

Methods

We applied the interstellar reddening law (Cardelli et al. 1989) to an incomplete sample of 17 low gravity L dwarfs with spectral types ranging from L0 to L7. We compared the dereddened spectra of the low gravity objects to a series of standard L dwarf spectra found in Kirkpatrick et al. 2010. The basic dereddening equation relies on three parameters, $A(V)$, R_v , and $E(B-V)$. These three parameters are related by the equation $R_v = A(V)/E(B-V)$. $A(V)$ is the absolute extinction in the V-band. $E(B-V)$, the color excess, equals $A(B) - A(V)$, where $A(B)$ is the absolute extinction in the B-band. We used $R_v = 3.1$, which is the standard value for the diffuse ISM. Figure 1 is a graphical depiction of the reddening function for a range of $E(B-V)$ values.

When applying the interstellar reddening law, we altered the value of $E(B-V)$ until we achieved a “best fit” between the low gravity object and the standard object. The best fit was determined by eye, and was defined as the fit for which the general spectral features fit most closely. When possible, we used low-resolution SpeX Prism spectra that made it easy to see whether the general shape of the spectra fit well.

Results

The interstellar reddening law effectively dereddened 15 of the 17 young objects. By saying an object was effectively dereddened, we mean that the general shape of the spectrum of the low gravity object matched up closely with that of the standard object after the reddening law was applied. For the 15 objects that were effectively dereddened, the $E(B-V)$ values ranged between 0.2 and 1.5. Table 1 lists the young object, the standard object, and the best $E(B-V)$ value. Figure 2 gives an example of an effectively dereddened object.

Two objects have no best $E(B-V)$ value. One object, 0355+1133, is the reddest known L dwarf. However, the general shape of its spectrum did not fit with the standard even for $E(B-V)$ well above those that worked for the other objects. Figure 3 shows attempts to find a best fit $E(B-V)$ for 0355+1133. The general shape of the spectrum of the object 0857+5708 already looked like the spectrum of the standard object, and required no dereddening.

Discussion

After dereddening the low gravity objects, we examined the ratio of the flux of the dereddened, young object to the flux of the standard object. Figure 4 gives an example of this ratio. The areas where this ratio deviates from 1 are the places where the dereddening function doesn't work. This may indicate that these spectral features are intrinsic to the object and are not a result of reddening due to cloud coverage. This is important because it may help us to determine which spectral features are indicative of a young object.

We also explored a possible relationship between $E(B-V)$ and spectral type. There was no clear relationship, but we also have a very small sample size. Figure 5 plots the best fit $E(B-V)$ value versus the L spectral type. Spectral types appended with a gamma indicate a very low gravity object, and spectral types appended with a beta indicate low gravity.

We tested the effect of applying the reddening law to optical spectra. The dereddening law actually had very little effect on the optical spectra. Figure 6 is the optical spectra of an object, dereddened with a variety of $E(B-V)$ values. All of the spectra look virtually the same, with very minor differences around 1 micron.

Conclusion

We conclude that the interstellar reddening law effectively dereddens the red NIR spectra of young, low gravity L dwarfs. Although unexpected, this result may help us to understand the kinds of particles that compose the dust in the L dwarfs atmosphere. The fact that the interstellar reddening law works leads us to the conclusion that there are small dust grains in the atmospheres of brown dwarfs. Our result may also help to disentangle trends between gravity, age, and cloud coverage. One way it can do this is by helping us identify spectral features that are specific to young objects and are unaffected by dereddening.

Now that we are aware of the degree to which the interstellar reddening law corrects for the atmospheric dust of L dwarfs, we can consider the physical properties of the dust (i.e. grain size, composition, etc.) Graduate student Kay Hiranaka is using Mie Theory to find dust compositions and sizes that would replicate the observed reddening that exists in the atmospheres of these objects.

References

- Cardelli, J.A., Clayton, G.C., & Mathis, J.S. Oct. 1989, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 345, 245.
- Cruz, K.L., Kirkpatrick, J.D., Burgasser, A.J. Feb. 2009, *The Astronomical Journal*, 137, 3345.
- Kirkpatrick, J.D. et al. 2010, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement*, 190, 100.
- Kirkpatrick, J.D. 2005, *Annual Review of Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 43, 195.
- O'Donnell, J.E. Feb. 1994, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 422, 158.

Tables and Figures

Low Gravity Object	Sp Type	Standard Object	Sp Type	Best E(B-V)	A(V)
03 57 26.95 -44 17 30.5	L0 β	03 45 43.16 +25 40 23.3	L0	0.3	0.93
15 52 59.06 +29 48 48.5	L0 β	03 45 43.16 +25 40 23.3	L0	0.4	1.24
03 23 10.02 -46 31 23.7	L0 γ	03 45 43.16 +25 40 23.3	L0	0.9	2.79
02 41 11.5 -03 26 58	L0 γ	03 45 43.16 +25 40 23.3	L0	0.7	2.17
17 11 13.5 +23 26 33	L0 γ	03 45 43.16 +25 40 23.3	L0	0.4	1.24
01 41 58.23 -46 33 57.4	L0 γ	03 45 43.16 +25 40 23.3	L0	0.6	1.86
05 36 19.9 -19 20 39	L1 β	21 30 44.64 -08 45 20.5	L1	1	3.1
10 22 48.21 +58 25 45.3	L1 β	21 30 44.64 -08 45 20.5	L1	0.2	0.62
01 17 47.4 -34 03 25	L1 β	21 30 44.64 -08 45 20.5	L1	0.5	1.55
00 45 21.43 +16 34 44.6	L2 β	13 05 40.1 -25 41 06	L2:	0.4	1.24
00 55 05.64 +01 34 36.5	L2 γ	13 05 40.1 -25 41 06	L2:	0.6	1.86
17 26 00.0 +15 38 19	L3 γ	15 06 54.4 +13 21 06	L3	0.6	1.86
18 41 08.61 +31 17 27.9	L4 β	21 58 04.5 -15 50 09	L4:	0.3	0.93
15 51 52.37 +09 41 14.8	L4 γ	21 58 04.5 -15 50 09	L4:	0.9	2.79
20 02 50.7 -05 21 52	L5 β	10 10 14.8 -04 06 49	L5	1.5	4.65
03 55 23.37 +11 33 43.7	L5 γ	15 07 47.6 -16 27 38	L5	None.	--
08 57 58.49 +57 08 51.4	L7	01 03 32.0 +19 35 36	L7	None.	--

Table 1. Our sample of 17 dereddened young objects, the standard used for each object, the spectral types of both objects, and the best E(B-V) value.

Figure 1. Flux ratio of dereddened flux to original flux vs. wavelength. This is a graphical depiction of the reddening law.

Figure 2. An example of an effectively dereddened low gravity L dwarf. The gray is the low gravity object prior to dereddening, the black is the low gravity object after dereddening, and the red is the standard object. (Normalized to the peak of J-band)

Figure 2: Attempts to deredden the NIR spectra of 0355+1133. The general spectral shape does not match up with that of the standard. The red line is an L5 standard, while the grey line is the unreddened spectra of 0355+1133. The black and blue lines are its dereddened spectra, with $E(B-V)$ values of 1.5 and 2.2, respectively.

Figure 4: Ratio of the flux of the dereddened object to the flux of the standard object vs. wavelength. The ratio is plotted in black, over the spectrum of the low gravity object (red) and the standard object (blue).

Figure 5: The best fit E(B-V) value versus the L spectral type for spectral types L0 through L5.

Figure 6. This is the optical spectrum of an object, dereddened with a variety of E(B-V) values, with each offset by a number. (Normalized around .825 microns)